

ADVANTAGES OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH

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ANNOTATION

The aim of the article is to show advantages of communicative approach and its effects on students' speech and connection between real life situations. The Communicative Approach is a way of teaching which is based on the principle that learning a language successfully involves communication rather than just memorizing a series of rules.

***Key words:** communication, real life situations, training, communicative approach, skill, speaking ability, social context, didactic and authentic material.*

Introduction

When teaching a foreign language, one of the difficulties is the fear of speaking associated with certain psychological complexes due to the inefficiency of language learning in the framework of the traditional approach at the previous stages of training. Another reason for difficulties in starting active communication in a foreign language is the established stereotypes that learning a foreign language is a complex and costly process in terms of both time and effort. An additional complexity that substantially impedes the effectiveness of training in the traditional approach is the use of artificial speech situations in the educational process. A communicative approach allows you to remove these restrictions. The use of typical everyday situations in training sessions encourages and motivates students to actively communicate. Language communication does not become far-fetched, but spontaneous and laid-back due to the relevance of the topics discussed. The communicative approach involves, above all, a pragmatic approach to learning a foreign language. It is aimed to prepare the listener for the use

of a foreign language in life, in everyday situations, rather than in a shorter time frame than to teach academic communication in the language.

Methodology and Analysis

One of the advantages of the communicative approach is communication with an “open ending”, in which the listeners manage their conversation themselves, and its outcome depends on the responses and reactions of the interlocutors in the group. In order to maintain interest in training sessions, each student selects and plays out new situations and organizes meaningful communication on topics that are important for pupils, involving the formation of skills to express a particular communicative intention (request, consent, invitation, refusal, advice, rebuke, etc.)

The obvious advantage of this technique is its psycholinguistic orientation, since a foreign language acts as a means of communication. When using traditional teaching methods, the student is inclined to consider a foreign language as an object of study, and not as an instrument of communication. Accordingly, the process of teaching a foreign language is often characterized by a state of anxiety of the listener, a fear of error.

Data collection And Result

The development of communicative language teaching was bolstered by new academic ideas. Before the growth of communicative language teaching, the primary method of language teaching was situational language teaching. This method was much more clinical in nature and relied less on direct communication. In Britain, applied linguists began to doubt the efficacy of situational language teaching. This was partly in response to Chomsky's insights into the nature of language. Chomsky had shown that the structural theories of language prevalent at the time could not explain the variety found in real communication. In addition, applied linguists such as Christopher Candlin and Henry Widdowson observed that the current model of language learning was ineffective in classrooms. They saw a need for students to develop communicative skill and functional competence in addition to mastering language structures.

Some fundamental provisions of the communicative approach are interpreted by specialists in the field of education in different ways. So, for example, some modern

foreign scientists believe that the learning process should be based only on the content side, real communication and exclude work on the linguistic form. To do this, it is necessary to use genuine communicative tasks that are adequate to the goal. The initial stage of training consists of discussions, role-playing games and modeling various events from everyday life. For schoolchildren at a higher level, intellectual games are used that increase their horizons and expand their understanding of the realities of the country of the language being studied. The first step to master the language is to memorize words, expressions, then pupils learn to use them when constructing in a real communicative situation, which group work is organized for: in pairs, triples, etc. The teacher creates all kinds of situations so that pupils can get a variety of communicative practice. At the first stage of training, the use of role-playing games promotes a higher learning efficiency. Listeners are offered all kinds of interesting situations, including intriguing and problematic ones. Various representations are played out, everyday life situations are played out, the main task of which is to improve speaking skills. Participants must get out of any difficult situation using only a foreign language.

Discussion and Conclusion

Speaking a second language, especially English, is getting more and more common between learners and, as a matter of fact the oral practice is being increasingly valued in the English language courses. Furthermore, speaking activities provide opportunities for rehearsal give both teacher and pupils' feedback and motivate pupils because of their engaging qualities and they contribute to the students' capacity of producing large conversational pattern and developing a variety of social contexts' arguments easily. It also showed the importance of didactic and authentic material related to the motivation of the schoolchildren during the practicing time; exercises based on the Communicative Competence to improve students' speaking and motivation to talk about a specific context, and finally, the influence that speaking activities can play on the pupils' written production.

In this study, it was concluded that the Communicative Approach plays an important role, contributing to the schoolchildren's oral production. It was identified that the speaking skill is one area that matters most pupil's time while learning a second

language; speaking activities perform an activate rather than a study function; the historical contribution concerning the Communicative Approach in order to help teachers understand how the process of teaching or learning was done and its importance to improve the teaching time.

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